

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT RESPONSE TO THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN GHANA'S PUBLIC SECTOR: THE EXPERIENCE OF THE DRIVER AND VEHICLE LICENSING AUTHORITY (DVLA)

AKPEKO AGBEVADE

Department of Political Science

School of Social Sciences, University Of Ghana, Legon

Email: aagbevade@ug.edu.gh

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6580-5393>

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: The aim of the study was to examine the human resource management interventions implemented by the Driver and Vehicle Licensing Authority in Ghana and how they shaped the work life balance of employees during the COVID-19 pandemic and the effect of the strategies on performance.

Design/Methodology: The study was a case study that deployed the mixed method and the person-environment fit theory.

Findings: The results indicate that the DVLA implemented a variety of strategies such as communication, training and development, performance management, employee health, safety and wellbeing. The strategies affected the work life balance of employees based on their marital status. Similarly, the strategies also impacted the performance of employees in various ways. Finally, the DVLA made some gains due to the interventions implemented.

Practical Implications: The strategies implemented at the height of the pandemic were knee-jet approaches; the work from home strategies affected the work life balance and performance of employees, however, significant results would have been attained if there were effective monitoring mechanisms in place. The paper recommends that HR practitioners should be proactive in policy issues and initiate monitoring and evaluation measures to tackle human resource issues at all times. The findings also confirm the assertion that human resource is the most important resource available to organisations and that if the appropriate human resource programmes are designed and implemented in a coordinated manner, organisations will surmount every difficulty including the COVID-19.

Originality/Value: The current study does not only make a significant contribution to the extant literature on COVID-19 and human resource management response strategies but also it brings to the fore practical responses to the pandemic based on empirical evidence from a specific public sector organisation (DVLA).

Keywords: Driver and Vehicle Licensing Authority, COVID-19, human resource management, work life balance, working from home, strategies, interventions

Paper type: Research Paper

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-CoV-2) was first detected in Wuhan, China on December 19, 2019. The World Health Organisation (WHO) declared it on March 11, 2020 as a global pandemic (World Health Organisation, 2020b; Azizi et al, 2021). Some scholars referred to it as human and health crises (Collings et al, 2021). The World Health Organization and the International Chamber of Commerce jointly postulated that, the pandemic must be tackled with dispatch by authorities to curtail its transmission because of its dual consequences on the health and economic sectors of countries (Azizi et al, 2021). On March 12, 2020, Ghana recorded its first two cases of the coronavirus (Ghana Health Service, 2020). Responding to it, government machinery observed the spread for couple of weeks across the globe (Asia, Europe and North America) and the tactics that nations implemented to avert escalation. The authorities in Ghana adapted the prescriptions of the WHO to satisfy the specific environmental needs of the State with the mindset that there is no single solution to addressing the menace. The general strategies to contain the spread of the virus were concentrated on suspension of public gatherings; disinfection of market facilities; strict enforcement of social distancing and good personal hygiene; closure of all land, sea, and air borders to human traffic and lockdown of the hotspots of the disease (Asante and Mills, 2020). Subsequent to these general measures, the Head of State in a nationwide address on 15 March 2020 placed a hold on all public gatherings for one month. Executive Instrument (E.I.) known as The Imposition of Restrictions Act 2020 (Act 1012) was enacted. In exercising the powers granted him under the Act, the President on March 27, 2020 announced a partial lockdown to take effect from March 30, 2020 in areas considered epicenters of the pandemic (Government of Ghana, March 27, 2020). The specific areas were the Greater Accra and Greater Kumasi. The COVID-19 is presently a herculean international health problem which have made organisations volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous with trickledown challenges such as business continuity and sustenance, minimal employee motivation, remote working and worsening unemployment (Azizi et al 2021).

The emergence of the deadly virus has influenced organisational workforce. The impact includes approach and method to work, employee relations, performance as well as human resource management practice. In response, human resource management practitioners have implemented diverse human resource management strategies to ensure that work continuous unimpeded to attain organisational goals while prioritizing the health, safety and wellbeing of employees.

In the wake of the pandemic, researches have been undertaken linking it (COVID-19) to human resource management practice. At its core, the COVID-19 pandemic is a human crisis. As a result, human resource (HR) leaders have been pivotal in seeking remedies to ameliorate its effect on organisational operations in the world. The COVID-19 is at variance with previous crises such as the global recession of 2008–09 or the Y2K crisis at the commencement of the millennium that emphasized the significance of finance and IT professionals respectively. By

amplifying the role of HR managers, COVID-19 has become a reference point with substantive implications for HR across the world (Collings et al 2021). In addition, the COVID-19 has made the human resource management practice environment a complicated and problematic one requiring professionals in the field to be proactive, creative, innovative and ingenious in proffering solutions to sustain their companies (Hamouche, 2021).

The discussion is also about the importance of HRM oriented strategies in shaping job performance through job related attitudes such as work motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in a time of crisis like the COVID-19 pandemic. Canevalea and Hatak (2020) examined challenges and opportunities that COVID-19 presents to HRM practice as well as the associated avenues for future research. Similarly, Iza (2020) underscored the fact that the outbreak of the pandemic brought untold hiccups on organisations with emphasis on HRM practice. Diep et al (2021) also discussed the human resource management practices adopted by organisations to make them resilient in the face of the COVID-19 and recommended investment in human resource capacity to make organisations resilient during crisis.

In Ghana, the COVID-19 brought about suspension of work and reorganisation of many economic and human resource activities. The pandemic impacted key HR practices in the Ghanaian formal sector. It also affected both parties in the employment contract; the employee and the employer were affected in jobs with regular hours of work and pay. Evidence in the Ghanaian setting showed that the initial three-week lockdown period in Accra and Kumasi which are considered the nucleus of public services and government agencies though remained opened had nonessential staff telecommuting leading to a 20% average decline in productivity (Adonu et al, 2020).

From the above, it can be gleaned that there exist some studies on COVID-19 pandemic and human resource management practice across the globe. They focused on the challenges, opportunities and the way forward. Others also addressed the specific HRM interventions implemented by organisations. However, most of these studies were general with no focus on specific organisations. Against this backdrop, this paper deployed the person-environment- fit (P-E-F) theory to examine the human resource management responses to the COVID-19 pandemic in Ghana's public sector using the Driver and Vehicle Licensing Authority (DVLA) as a reference point. Specifically, the study was guided by three-fold research objectives, namely; to

- (i) Interrogate the DVLA's HRM strategies in response to the pandemic,
- (ii) Examine the nexus between the HRM strategies implemented and work-life balance of the employees, and
- iii) Analyze the linkage between the HRM strategies implemented and organizational performance.

The Ghanaian public sector is considered because it is the highest employer in Ghana and during the partial lockdown, employees of most state institutions were going to work. The

DVLA is selected because it is considered as a “pocket of effectiveness (PoE)” in Ghana’s public sector and the HR department was adjudged the best public sector organisation in human resource management practice for the year 2020 (Agbevade, 2022).

Structurally, the paper is segmented into six sections. These are the state of the art literature on COVID-19 and human resource management practice, theoretical taxonomy, methodology, findings, discussion, conclusion and recommendations.

STATE OF THE ART LITERATURE ON COVID-19 AND HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICE

Shock caused by the COVID-19 pandemic had considerable impacts on Ghanaian businesses, forcing many firms to cut cost by reducing staff hours, cutting wages, and in some cases laying off workers. An envisaged number of 770,000 workers (25.7% of the total workforce), had their wages reduced and about 42,000 employees were laid off during the country’s partial lockdown. The pandemic also led to reduction in working hours for close to 700,000 workers (Ghana Statistical Service, UNDP and the World Bank, August 2020).

Adonu et al (2020) examined the impact of the COVID-19 on key HR practices in the Ghanaian formal sector. They estimated that the emergence of the pandemic had affected both the employer and employee in terms of hours of work and pay. For instance, the lockdown period culminated into a 20% reduction in employee output though non-essential employees were telecommuting. At the employees’ front, the pandemic had physical, spiritual, emotional and psychological effect on them because of deferred medical check-up due to fear of infection at health care facilities. To add, restrictions on religious and recreational programmes affected employees’ physical, emotional, spiritual and psychological wellbeing.

Risk of infection at workplaces and discomfort arising from wearing facemask compromised the welfare and safety of the Ghanaian worker. Another sphere of the impact on employees was striking a balance between work, family and social life. Employees’ most especially female workers (it is estimated that they spend about 9 hours a day in providing unpaid care services) were affected because of the responsibility of caring for their children due to the closure of schools. This affected their ability to concentrate on the work.

Career shock was another area of inhibition by the virus. A career shock is a disruptive event which is outside the control of employees but affects their career with positive or negative impacts and at various intensities, frequencies and predictability is experienced by employees in pandemics (Akkermans et. al, 2020). Employees in the Ghanaian formal sector experienced career shocks in the form of promotion deferments, pay cuts and job losses. A survey conducted in selected state enterprises in Ghana indicated that 50% of employees had their promotions deferred in 2020 (Nantwi, 2020). In addition, comparing the service and the manufacturing subsectors, the service sector had 6% rate of promotions than manufacturing. Some institutions offered promotions with retrospective effects without the corresponding rewards for employees.

Employees accepted these overtures because they were concerned with retaining their jobs amidst the crisis.

The emergence of the pandemic changed work arrangements in the formal sector. This has posed a challenge to the employer, as they have to formulate and implement programmes that will make the organisation resilient, recover without downsizing and reducing employee morale. In response, most organisations in Ghana implemented strategies such as adoption of new technologies, recruitment and selection, remote working, staff rationalization etc (Adonu et al, 2020).

Davidescu et al (2020) investigated the effect of flexible working time and places, such as total home office, partial home office, flex office, and co-working, on the job satisfaction and performance of Romanian employees in order to design sustainable human resource management policies at the national level. Results of their work showed that the main forms of work flexibility, such as home office and employee turnover, have been applied in the Romanian labor market to some degree. One-third of Romanian employees opined that the flexibility strategy was implemented, but little attention was given to flexible working hours and days, shift working, and overtime. In terms of workplace flexibility, working from home was most welcomed by the employees, while the working from home strategy was implemented to a very little extent.

Radic et al., (2020) in contributing to the debate on HRM strategies and COVID-19 found that companies did not have a proper human resource management strategy during the COVID-19 pandemic. In view of this, employees had psychological problems with resultant outcomes including anxiety, depression and stress among employees during the peak of the pandemic. This made employees despair and despondent thereby losing hope and trust in their companies. Furthermore, the employees became frustrated, experienced low morale, low job satisfaction and lack of commitment to organizational mission and vision.

In contributing to the literature on COVID-19, Azizi et al (2021) identified the following as the obstacles of COVID-19: economic shock, changing social behaviors, challenges at the organisational level. They also interrogated the strategies deployed in responding to the crisis. They enumerated flexibility, use of cyberspace in work-related activities, staff safety, focus on working conditions, participation, development, and motivation of employees by continuous communication with them and use of creative methods, provision of training courses for employees, use of creative ways to support employees and ensure their health and well-being. Other strategies identified were deployment of creative fun activities for employees, ensuring adequate provision for efficient and distance working, strengthening internal efficiency and gaining talent, commitment of managers, selection and participation of employees in decision-making, strengthening cohesion and sharing experiences, and making necessary changes based on organisational assessment and data.

There is a significant role of COVID-19 oriented HRM strategies in shaping job performance through job related attitudes such as work motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in a time of crisis occurring in the organisation due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Their findings revealed that organisations employed a blend of "hard" HRM strategies related to the financial aspects and "soft" HRM strategies related to keeping employees' wellbeing during the crisis. This shaped job performance through job-related attitudes and consequently strengthening organisational performance.

Organisations were faced with grand difficulties of unparalleled proportions. This forced them to dive into and directly manage unprecedented territory as they altered their workforce in technical, physical and socio-psychological ways not witnessed before the outbreak of the COVID-19. The pandemic created the environment for human resource management (HRM) – with managers having to quickly venture into the unknown unknowns as they strived to help their workforce adapt to and cope with radical changes occurring in the work and social environment. They further examined the challenges and opportunities that COVID-19 presented to HRM practice as well as the associated possibilities for future research. They identified the following setbacks of the pandemic to HRM practice: adjusting new and current employees to drastically change work conditions, such as shifting to remote work environments or implementing new workplace policies and procedures to limit human contact. Three effects of the COVID-19 on employees were identified, namely; the erosion of fit, disproportionate work-family effects and disproportionate effect on alternative family structure. They proposed the use of entrepreneurship to tackle the issue of employee adjustment and wellbeing. They underscored entrepreneurial values such as autonomy, designing of perfect jobs, tolerance of uncertainty, approaching new issues openly and proactively. They also admonished HR practitioners to design jobs taking into consideration some of these entrepreneurial values.

Collings et al (2021) described the disease as a human crisis which has attracted the attention of human resource managers across the globe. In their view, COVID-19 has amended the experience of work for the vast majority of employees. It forced organisations to streamline how work is organised and how jobs are designed. The potential for fractures between employee groups has been brought to the fore. For example between those who can WFH and those who cannot, those who remained on payroll versus those furloughed, and even those in different business units impacted differently by the pandemic. In contributing to the literature on HR response to the pandemic, Collings et al (2021) advocated for the execution of a heterogeneous instead of a homogeneous strategic human resource management interventions due to the diversity of employees and the amorphous and wicked nature of the COVID-19 pandemic. In fact, the COVID-19 has been described as a wicked problem because of the political, social, economic and cultural connotations, the complexity of actors, diverse and multiple information and policy options and choices required and available in dealing with it (Ayee, 2022). In this regard, they opined that the COVID-19 has exposed the excessive focus on shareholders in organisations. In their findings, the pandemic has highlighted the significance of other

organisational actors such as employees, customers, the locality of the organisation and corporate social responsibility.

Diep et al (2021) examined specific human resource practices adopted to develop organisational resilience capacity in times of crises. Their study provides an informed perspective that supports investment in human resource (HR) policies that facilitates resilience capabilities during crisis. Extending scholarship on HRM in crisis moment, Hillyard (2000) argued that the discipline could provide organizations with two significant contributions: (i) operational capabilities to manage crises and (ii) interventions to facilitate collective and individual organizational performance that improves crisis responses. Studies have noted the prevalence of cost reduction measures in response to recession such as layoffs, payroll cuts, recruitment freezes, reductions in training, rigorous performance management or downsizing, rather than maintaining the whole system (Israeli et al., 2011). In other cases, organisations sought to reinforce their capabilities rather than adopting cost reduction measures alone. Teague and Roche (2014) identified two categories of HR practices employed during crises: technical and behavioural. Technical refers to practices relevant to cost and headcount reduction, while behavioural consists of practices that facilitate employee motivation and commitment.

Human resource management interventions before the lockdown to enhance employee resilience were targeted at employee health and safety and positive psychology to ensure employee wellbeing. Studies have found that during COVID-19 lockdown, HR strategies implemented could be grouped into economic capital enhancing practices, social capital enhancing practices, sharing culture and diffused power and accountability practices. Most of the post-lockdown strategies implemented were resource network, talent management, job redeployment and performance management.

Diep et al (2021) intimated that the success of these HR resilient strategies hinges on dynamics such as organisational, financial, people-oriented organisational culture, leadership with focus on people-oriented sharing and ethical values and the business vision and mission. Companies exhibited three types of attitudes towards their employees at the pick of the COVID-19. These were some companies closed and hence dismissed all employees, others retained their employees by sending or granting them unpaid leaves and some retained employees through giving them salaries. However, most companies retained their senior staff with salaries. Companies also responded to the pandemic variously, whereas the recruitment of new staff was reduced in some, others hired only temporarily staff with contract to carry out ongoing projects (Iza, 2020).

The pandemic brought about high rate of labour attrition because of the disparity between management and employees' values. Employees stayed because they had no option at the time but were demotivated. This affected the quality of service, products and clients. Employees not fired had psychological stress, fear and anxiety. This negatively affected their loyalty to the company. Those who left went away with their worth of experience, skills etc and organisational

culture was ultimately affected. According to experts, the main hurdle was that companies had to switch to different behaviours i.e. working from office to remote working systems using online tools. However, not everyone was able or ready to make such big alterations, but they rather suspended the operations until the virus passed, as they believed that everything would revert to business as usual.

The above reviews gives us adequate grounds that empirically missing in the academic discourse is a devoted study on HRM response to COVID-19 in Ghana's public sector. This study makes a modest addition to the literature as the findings would help unravel how the DVLA responded to the pandemic with respect to HR practice and it provides a policy framework for HR practice in times of crisis management in Ghana's public sector.

Theoretical Taxonomy

The study employed the Person-Environment-Fit (PEF) theory. The PEF theory posits that individuals were attracted to and selected by organizations whose work environments reflect the same values, cultures, and work features as their own important beliefs, values, and desires (Kristof-Brown & Guay, 2011). Based on these processes, employees who enter organisations where their P-E fit is maximized typically flourished and experienced heightened levels of satisfaction, engagement, and overall well-being (KristofBrown, Zimmerman, & Johnson, 2005). However, when the work environment that supported the fulfillment of these needs and desires is changed as witnessed during the COVID19 pandemic, the needs of the employee and the work environment results in misfit with the tendency of influencing the performance of employees (Follmer, Talbot, Kristof-Brown, Astrove, & Billsberry, 2018). The P-E fit also seeks to establish a bond between the employees and the organisation as well as between fellow staff.

In the words of McKibbin and Fernando (2020), throughout the whole process of recruitment, potential employees were always attracted to an organisation based on this major or fundamental objective. Nevertheless, as most organisations adjust to new forms of working due to COVID-19, physical interactions were bound to reduce or permanently diminish hence the newfound P-E is incongruent with spillover effect on productivity and wellbeing of the workforce and the organisation as a whole (He & Harris, 2020).

Similarly, Khudhair et al. (2020) asserted that with the emergence of the COVID-19, organisations not familiar with new forms of operating organizations such as working remotely recorded low output. Studies have shown that enhancing employee commitment through remote working and consequently maintaining a good working relationship between the employees and the organisation requires implementation of strategic policies and procedures. These are sometimes difficult to fulfil in some organisation especially in crisis moments (COVID-19) where resources to support such initiatives were scarce (Lauer et al., 2020; Stavros, Melfou, & Papaevangelou, 2020). This study deployed the P-E fit theory to assess the HRM strategies implemented by the DVLA at the height of the pandemic, how it affected employees work switch and its effect on employee productivity.

Profile of the Driver and Vehicle Licensing Authority

The DVLA is an agency under the Ministry of Transport. It was established by Act 569 of 1999 to replace the Vehicle Examination and Licensing Division (VELD). The DVLA as a regulatory agency is clothed with the authority to enhance effective administration of drivers and vehicles. It was weaned off government subvention in March 2016.

The mission of the Authority is to ensure best practices for licensing drivers and vehicles to promote road safety and environmental sustainability, while pursuing integrity, excellence, professionalism and reliability in service delivery. In terms of vision, the DVLA is to be a reputable organisation with internationally accepted standards for driver and vehicle licensing.

The DVLA does not work in isolation, rather it works with stakeholders such as Motor Transport and Traffic Department (MTTD) of the Ghana Police Service; Transport Associations; National Road Safety Commission; Ghana National Insurance Commission; Ghana Automobile Distribution Association; Government Technical Training Centre; National Drivers Academy, the Judiciary and the Motoring Public. The DVLA is a legal entity hence has the power to sue and can be sued.

According to the DVLA Act 569, 1999, the Authority is responsible for ensuring that only qualified people are in possession of drivers' license and only fit motor vehicles should be on the roads. In addition, it also ensures that institutions with the requisite human resource and logistics provide services in building the capacity of prospective drivers and keeping proper records on all its clients. The Authority also provides policy advisory services to the Minister responsible for transport (Republic of Ghana, 1999).

METHODOLOGY

The study is a case study type which used the mixed method. Data was collected both qualitatively and quantitatively. Qualitative data was collected through face-to-face interview from the human resource unit of the Authority on the HR strategies implemented during the pandemic. Quantitative data was gathered using the questionnaire on the effect of the HR strategies pertaining to the various HR roles such as health, safety and wellbeing, performance, work life balance among others. The study used the purposive sampling to collect qualitative data while simple random sampling was used for the quantitative data. A sample size of 70 was drawn from the employees of the Greater Accra Region which is the macrocosm of the Authority. Data was collected between August and October 2022. The data was analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. Validity and reliability were enhanced through member checking.

FINDINGS

This section of the paper is devoted to the presentation and analysis of the three-fold objectives that underlined the study.

Objective 1: To interrogate the DVLA's HRM strategies in response to the pandemic.

It is instructive to state that at each stage of the pandemic in Ghana, no public sector employee lost the job and none suffered a salary cut hence the staff capacity of the DVLA was intact, as such management was preoccupied with the formulation and implementation of HR strategies and policies that would ensure the attainment of the Authority's goals. It is also important to note that the DVLA implemented pre-lockdown, partial lockdown and post-lockdown strategies, however, the strategies implemented in these three were the same. These strategies now engage our attention. The Authority implemented five key HR intervention strategies. These were communication, health safety and wellbeing, human resource development, employee performance management, and rewards and motivation.

First, communication. Communication is the transmission of information or message from one person or group of persons to another person or group of persons with the sender getting a feedback from the recipient. Communication is incomplete unless the sender receives a feedback. In responding to the COVID-19, the management of DVLA allowed for both downward and upward communication. The downward communication was from management to the staff. This took the form of awareness creation among employees on the pandemic, how to conduct oneself to avoid contracting it, the Authority also pasted notices at vantage points throughout its offices on the dos and don'ts on the COVID-19 among others. The staff also gave feedback to the management on the information received through upward communication. Communication channels such as the internal mail system, WhatsApp and zoom meetings were deployed to relay messages to the employees and vice versa. In addition, both written and non-written (posters, pictures on hand washing, approaches to coughing to avoid spreading the virus etc) communication were utilized.

Second is health, safety, and wellbeing. It refers to programmes aimed at protecting employees and other people affected by what a company produces or does against the hazards arising from their employment or their links with the company (Armstrong, 2009). For the assurance of the health and safety of employees, the Authority distributed personal protective equipment (PPE) across all the 33 branches. A committee headed by a senior principal HR officer was designated for the management and distribution of PPEs and related matters. The decentralization approach was used where branches received the PPEs every fortnight for distribution to their members of staff. Items distributed were customized nose masks, hand sanitizers, hand washbasins, dispensers, liquid soap and tissue papers. In addition, there were standby health officers to attend to affected staff. Also, infested staff were given the fourteen days mandatory quarantine and if not fit, they had extra days for treatment. This was aimed at ensuring that the staff were safe from the virus.

The third HR intervention was training and development. This intervention was aimed at developing the capacity of the employees in relation to handling work related issues during the pandemic. To avoid congestion and overcrowding in the offices, training programmes were organised for heads of units who later organized same training for the members of their units. The tailor-made trainings were in the following areas: vehicle examination, performance

management for unit heads to align employee performance evaluation to the exigencies of the time, project management, the use of Microsoft office, network and information security.

The fourth HR intervention was on ensuring employee performance management. Performance management simply refers to measures organisations deploy to improve individual and team performance. To ensure continuity of work, the Authority adopted measures such as biweekly work rotation. Under this strategy, employees were divided into groups with each of the 14 units represented in each group. A group works for two weeks and was replaced by another group. In addition, remote working or working from home (WFH) driven by e-governance apparatus was employed. The Government to Citizen (G2C) model of e-government was used. This model permits government institutions and officials to use state institution's websites, emails to inform citizens (clients) of government operations and allows clients to transact businesses with the state institutions (Authority) online. The transactions were application for license, renewal of roadworthy certificates, and vehicle registration among others. With technology, the employees periodically updated clients on the state of their requests to reduce congestion and make room for social distancing at the various stations of the Authority. The updates were done through emails, telephone calls and text messages.

The fifth HR intervention was reward and motivation. The Authority realized the importance of sustaining the zeal and commitment of employees during the pandemic; hence, a reward system was introduced to motivate the employees to give off their best. Aside the monthly salary, employees were given extra money depending on the rank as incentives to motivate them whenever their shift was on duty. Furthermore, unit heads were encouraged to check on their unit members. These strategies fostered a sense of togetherness and belongingness among the employees, as they felt loved and accepted at a time when people (employees) were concerned about their personal safety at work usually expressed in the Ghanaian parlance "*each one for himself, God for us all*".

Objective 2: To examine the nexus between the HRM strategies implemented and work-life balance.

Work life balance (WLB) refers to the harmony between family and work responsibilities. A balanced work life reduces the likelihood of conflict between the two responsibilities. However, the absence of balance results in work-family conflict. The findings are illustrated below.

To determine the relationship between marital status and work life balance, Table 1 below depicts the extent to which marital status affected employees working from home positively. From Table 1 below, 10 respondents (16%) who were bachelors/spinsters strongly disagreed that WFH affected their family life positively. Four (4) respondents representing 6% each who were bachelors/spinsters disagreed and were neutral that WFH affected their family life positively. Six (6) respondents (9%) each agreed and strongly agreed that WFH positively affected their family lives. With respect to the divorced employees, one (1) each representing 2% strongly disagreed and strongly agreed that WFH affected their family lives.

Table 1: Relationship between marital status and working from home affected my family life positively

		Working from home affected my family life positively					Total
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Marital status	Bachelor/Spinster	10	4	4	6	6	30
	Divorced	1	0	0	0	1	2
	Married	14	5	5	5	3	32
Total		25	9	9	11	10	64

Source: Fieldwork, October 2022

On the part of the married respondents, 14 of the respondents representing 22% strongly disagreed that WFH affected their family lives. Five (5) each of the respondents (8%) disagreed and agreed that WFH positively affected their family lives and another five (5) respondents were neutral. Three (3) of the married respondents representing 5% strongly agreed that WFH positively affected their family lives. The above explanation is demonstrated on Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Relationship between marital status and working from home
Source: Field work, October 2022

Table 2 and Figure 2 presents the relationship between working from home and negative family life. From the table, it can be gleaned that 11 respondents (17%) who were bachelors/spinsters strongly disagreed that WFH negatively affected their family lives while seven (7) representing

11%, four (4) representing 6% and 3 respondents representing 5% indicated agreed and strongly agreed respectively and another four (4) respondents representing 6% were neutral. Two (2) respondents representing 3% of the divorced respondents strongly disagreed that WFH affected their family lives negatively. Fourteen respondents representing 22%, seven (7) respondents representing 11%, and three (3) respondents representing 5% indicated strongly disagreed, disagreed, agreed and strongly agreed respectively whiles four (4) of the respondents representing 6% were neutral.

Table 2: Relationship between working from home and negative family life

		Working from home affected my family life negatively					Total
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Marital status	Bachelor/Spinster	11	7	4	4	3	29
	Divorced	2	0	0	0	0	2
	Married	14	7	4	3	3	31
Total		27	14	8	7	6	62

Source: Field work, October 2022

Figure 2: Relationship between working from home and negative family life

Source: Field work, October 2022

The study also ascertained the relationship between working from home and taking care of family. This is illustrated in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Relationship between marital status and working from home

		Working from home allowed me time to take care of my family					Total
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Marital status	Bachelor/Spinster	7	6	4	9	3	29
	Divorced	1	0	0	0	1	2
	Married	10	2	8	5	7	32
Total		18	8	12	14	11	63

Source: Field work, October, 2022

From Table 3, it can be distilled that seven (7), six (6), nine (9) and three (3) respondents representing 11%, 9%, 14% and 5% respectively indicated strongly disagreed, disagreed, agreed and strongly agreed respectively whiles four (4) of the respondents representing 6% were neutral. One of the respondents who was divorced strongly disagreed that WFH allowed to take care of the family and another single respondent strongly agreed that WFH allowed for taking care of family. With respect to the married respondents, eighteen (18), eight (8), fourteen (14) and eleven (11) respondents representing 28%, 13%, 22% and 17% respectively correspondingly responded as follows: strongly disagreed, disagreed, agreed and strongly agreed whiles 12 respondents representing 19% were neutral. This is illustrated in Figure 3 below

Figure 3: Relationship between working from home and taking care of family

Source: Field work, October 2022

Objective 3: The nexus between HRM strategies implemented and performance.

On the connection between the various HR interventions and performance, bachelors and spinsters responded as follows: two (2), one (1), twelve (12) and seven (7) representing 3%, 2%,

19% and 11% respectively indicated strongly disagreed, disagreed, agreed and strongly agreed correspondingly. Eight (8) of the respondents representing 13% were neutral.

One (1) divorced respondent representing 2% disagreed that the HR interventions shaped their performance while one divorced respondent was also neutral about the linkage between the HR interventions and performance. The responses from the married respondents were as follows: nine (9), two (2), eight (8) and six (6) representing 14%, 3%, 13% and 9% respectively indicated strongly disagreed, agreed, and strongly agreed respectively with 16 respondents representing 25% being neutral on the connection between the two variables. The responses are depicted in Table 4 and Figure 4 below.

Table 4: Relationship between HR interventions and performance

		COVID-19 HR interventions generally help improve my performance					Total
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Marital status	Bachelor/Spinster	2	1	8	12	7	30
	Divorced	0	1	1	0	0	2
	Married	9	2	7	8	6	32
Total		11	4	16	20	13	64

Source: Field work, October 2022

Figure 4: Relationship between HR interventions and performance

Source: Field work, October 2022

The finding is further corroborated with qualitative data from the audited accounts of the DVLA. The audited accounts by the Ghana Audit Service revealed that 2020 witnessed a 27% increase

in total actual revenue over that of 2019. Thus, from GH¢173,016,303.03 in 2019 to GH¢220,073,377.52 in 2020.

DISCUSSIONS

The study interrogated the HRM strategy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic using the DVLA as a reference point in Ghana's public sector. It became known that the management of the Authority did implement key HRM strategies such as communication, employee health, safety and wellbeing, training and development, performance management, rewards and motivation. These strategies were aimed at equipping employees with the requisite knowledge, skills and abilities (KSA) to deliver on the mandate of the Authority. The communication strategy was not limited to only the employees but was extended to clients as well through the periodic updates given to the clients on their services. Embedded in the strategies was the avoidance of overcrowding in offices and the premises of the Authority by both employees and clients. This measure is in conformity with the general mantra of social distancing. There was interconnection between the strategies implemented. This culminated into coordination, coherence and synergy for the desired productivity.

On the linkage between the HRM strategies and WLB, the findings were mixed, as the extent of impact on WLB was dependent on the family life (married, divorced or single) of the respondent. Generally, the impact of the HRM strategies such as remote working, telecommuting and WFH did not significantly affect the employees, due to the absence of monitoring mechanisms and previous experience; hence, most of the decisions were non-programmed.

On the effect of the HR strategies on employee performance, the findings revealed that the strategies implemented did shape the performance of employees, as the financial performance of the Authority for 2020 (COVID-19 year) indicated a 27% increase in actual revenue over that of 2019.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study examined the HRM strategies formulated and implemented by the DVLA in coping with the COVID-19 menace and found the following as the strategies implemented: communication, employee health, safety and wellbeing, training and development, performance management and rewards and motivation. The strategies did influence the work life balance of employees in a mixed manner based on the nature of the employees' family life. Finally, the strategies did affect the performance of employees as shown in the 2020 Ghana Audit Service report of the DVLA.

Drawing from the findings, the study recommends that human resource management practitioners across all sectors must be proactive in the practice to avoid reactionary measures in dealing with crises such as the COVID-19. In addition, effective monitoring mechanisms should be instituted to help manage employee performance when employees are WFH. The measures could include the use of SMART goal mechanisms coupled with both qualitative and quantitative goals. Furthermore, this study employed a single case study; future studies can do

multiple case study by comparing either public or private sector organisations to examine the similarities and differences in HRM strategy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic for the purposes of best practices.

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